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LANGUAGE EDUCATION AS A RESULT OF LEARNING THE LANGUAGE AND CULTURE OF THE PEOPLE

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Abstract: *This article examines issues of language teaching: problems of language education, the system of scientific knowledge related to the subject of study, the subject of speech activity. The current state of language education, the need to prepare an independent user of the language, as well as the components of communicative competence are presented. In addition, the current state of linguistics is outlined. The main subjects of linguistics: speech, speech activity, subject of speech, speech behavior, real processes of formation of speech communication, its acquisition and conditions.*

Keywords: *linguacultural studies and linguistic and regional studies, psychological foundations of language teaching, language teaching methods, didactics, goals, objectives, social subject.*

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ КАК РЕЗУЛЬТАТ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И КУЛЬТУРЫ НАРОДА

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы обучения языку: проблемы языкового образования, система научных знаний, связанных с предметом изучения, предмет речевой деятельности. Представлено современное состояние языкового образования, необходимость подготовки самостоятельного пользователя языка, а также компоненты коммуникативной компетенции. Кроме того, изложено современное состояние языкознания. Основные предметы языкознания: речь, речевая деятельность, субъект речи, речевое поведение, реальные процессы формирования речевого общения, его усвоение и условия.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвокультурология и лингвострановедение, психологические основы обучения языку, методика обучения языку, дидактика, цели, задачи, социальный субъект.*

TILSHUNOSLIK TA'LIMI XALQ MADANIYATI VA TILINI O'RGANISHNING NATIJASIDIR

***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada til o'qitish masalalari: tilshunoslik muammolari, o'rganish mavzusiga oid ilmiy bilimlar tizimi, nutq faoliyatining predmeti, tilshunoslikning hozirgi holati, mustaqil til foydalanuvchisini tayyorlash zarurati, shuningdek, kommunikativ kompetentsiyaning tarkibiy qismlari ko'rsatilgan. Bundan tashqari, tilshunoslikning hozirgi holati ko'rsatilgan. Tilshunoslikning asosiy predmetlari: nutq, nutq faoliyati, nutq predmeti, nutqiy xulq-atvor, nutqiy muloqotni shakllantirishning real jarayonlari, uning o'zlashtirilishi va shartlari.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** lingvokulturologiya va lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, til o'qitishning psixologik asoslari, til o'rgatish metodikasi, didaktika, maqsad, vazifalar, ijtimoiy sub'ekt.*

The result of language education is a formed linguistic personality. Its formation is a long process that continues until the linguistic potential of the individual undergoes changes.

A linguistic personality is an abstract, autonomously existing, individual linguistic system that is formed on the basis of "innate psychophysiological characteristics" (A. A. Leontiev) of a person, under the influence of speech communication, when comprehending the language system in the process of its study, in independent speech activity, taking into account social conditions and the professional orientation of the person. An individual linguistic system provides a native speaker with the ability to perform speech acts classified by types of speech activity (reading, writing, speaking, listening) and by language levels (phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic) (Yu. N. Karaulov).

Yu. N. Karaulov put forward the idea of a leveled organization of the linguistic personality, which includes:

verbal-semantic level, called zero (personality lexicon); logical-cognitive level, qualified as the first (personality thesaurus); level of activity-communicative needs of a person, designated as the second (personality pragmatic on).

Personality lexicon - a stock of words, expressions that a native speaker learns based on imitation of the speech of other people, in the learning process - includes, first of all, units serving the everyday sphere of communication between people and used at the level of automated skill in typical constructions for establishing and developing contacts between communicators.

Personality thesaurus is formed by generalized concepts. Such units (definitions, aphorisms, phraseological units, proverbs, sayings, catchphrases), reflecting the picture of the world of native speakers, are used for the exchange of information and interaction of people in the process of their joint activities, including educational ones, and serve the purposes of developing speech and transforming the source text. The pragmatic on of the personality - the system of its goals, motives, intentions - is made up of communicative-activity needs that guide the development of the linguistic personality, regulate its speech behavior, speech activity, and create a system of meanings and values of the linguistic model of the world of the personality. The target setting for the use of language tools at this level of formation of the linguistic personality is their choice in accordance with the social conditions of communication. G. I. Bogin associates the concept of "linguistic personality" with relatively complete mastery of the language and therefore names various types of speech activity and aspects of language as its levels; L. P. Krysin distinguishes linguistic, national-cultural, encyclopedic and situational levels in the structure of linguistic personality. The concept of "linguistic personality" is especially relevant, according to M. R. Lvov, for teaching language at school. Belarusian methodologist N. G. Yelensky identifies the system-forming concepts of the core of the linguistic personality of a student (knowledge of the language system, speech abilities as individual psychological characteristics of the personality) and establishes its structure, which includes cognitive, lexical-grammatical, pragmatic, lingua-cultural, motivational-emotive segments.

1.2. Language education as a system

The planned result of language education can be achieved as a result of the functioning of a certain system and its varieties. There are systems of social institutions and educational processes of language education.

The social institutions that organize language education include: government bodies of republican, regional, city, district significance; the regulatory framework; educational levels (primary, basic, secondary, higher education) and types of educational institutions (comprehensive school, gymnasium, lyceum, higher educational institution).

The system of educational processes of language education consists of:

social order of society;

methodical science (linguodidactics and methodology of language teaching);

the goal, approaches, principles, content of language teaching, implemented in the educational standard, concept, program, textbooks and other teaching aids;

teacher, the goal of language teaching, the activity of language teaching, the result of language teaching;

student, the goal of language learning, the activity of language learning, the result of language acquisition.

The main functions of the language education system are systematic language teaching, native and non-native, and education by means of the subject. Mastering the native language allows the language personality to communicate freely in the chosen field of activity due to the formation of linguistic, communicative, socio-cultural competencies. Mastering a non-native language, including a foreign one, allows the secondary language personality to communicate indirectly and/or directly with native speakers of this language, successfully navigating in the modern multilingual and multicultural world.

Linguodidactics is a theory of language teaching, the integration of linguistics and didactics, providing a scientific basis for: language teaching strategies, approaches to its organization, goals, planned results, principles, content, methods and organizational forms. The object of linguodidactics is the general theory of language

teaching (theoretical justification of the process of teaching/learning a language without taking into account the conditions in which the process takes place and the status of the language) and its provision (concepts, content of language education, organizational forms of teaching, mechanisms for research and design of the learning process).

The subject of linguodidactics is the identification of general patterns of interaction between language teaching, learning it (teacher's activity) and its acquisition (student's activity), scientifically substantiated criteria for selecting the content of training and technologies for acquiring personalized knowledge; selection of principles for organizing training and its goals, methods, organizational forms, and teaching aids. In other words, the subject of linguodidactics is a system of generalized ideas about the processes of learning a language, its acquisition by students from the standpoint of modern views on the learning process.

Linguodidactics studies the problems of the goals and content of language teaching (its selection and organization), the laws of mastering any language, regardless of whether it is the first, second or foreign language, and the development of teaching aids.

The central figure of linguodidactics as a theory of teaching languages is the linguodidactic model of the linguistic personality (G.I. Bogin).

Linguodidactics is called upon to:

- understand and describe the linguocognitive structure of the linguistic personality,
- substantiate the conditions and patterns of its development as an expected result in the process of teaching and learning a language,
- study the specifics of both teaching/learning (language, linguistic picture of the world of a native speaker of the studied language), and the interaction of all subjects of this process, the nature of errors (linguistic, cultural) and the mechanism for their elimination/prevention.

The functions of linguodidactics as a theory of teaching a language are established taking into account that the process of teaching a language is simultaneously an object of scientific study and an object of construction (modeling).

The following functions of linguodidactics are distinguished:

- scientific and theoretical (description of the language learning process, revealing the patterns and essence of its organization at the time of the study or in historical retrospect, which opens up the possibility of foresight - transformation of the language learning process based on the predictive potential of the acquired knowledge);
- constructive and modeling (transformation of the learning process: its construction, modeling based on the acquired knowledge, with the purpose of improvement, which is embodied in the linguodidactic systems, norms, rules, recommendations, etc. developed by the researcher);
- integrative (combination of scientific achievements of philosophers, linguists, teachers, psychologists, methodologists, specialists in communication theory and computer science with the purpose of reliable substantiation of the language learning process).

The purpose of linguodidactics is to study the problems of analysis, management, modeling of language acquisition processes.

The tasks solved by linguodidactics:

- □ development of theoretical foundations of language education concepts – linguacentric and anthropocentric;
- □ description and explanation of the essence of the language teaching process and the conditions for its effectiveness;
- □ theoretical substantiation of methodological systems of language teaching, the components of which are the goals of subject education, principles of selection and structuring of educational material, means, methods and techniques of language teaching, forms and methods of current and midterm control;
- □ theoretical substantiation and understanding of emerging organizational forms of language teaching, innovative teaching systems and technologies.
- The solution of the tasks facing linguodidactics and the implementation of the formulated functions is carried out with the involvement of a system of concepts

belonging to various branches of knowledge. The main concepts and categories used by linguodidactics:

- □ philosophical concepts: form and content, general and singular, cause and effect; possibility and reality, quantity and quality, theory and practice, law and regularity, etc.;
- □ general scientific concepts: structure, function, organization, process, concept, approach, aspect, activity, principle, etc.;
- □ general concepts of pedagogy: education, development, upbringing, pedagogical experiment, pedagogical process, pedagogical monitoring, etc.;
- □ specific concepts of linguodidactics: language teaching, language learning, native language (foreign language) as an academic subject, educational material, educational situation, principles, methods and techniques of language teaching, etc.;
- □ concepts borrowed from related sciences:

psychology (perception, comprehension, assimilation, memory, thinking, mental development, etc.);

logic (induction, deduction, analysis, synthesis, generalization, classification, systematization, etc.);

cybernetics (feedback, dynamic system);

psycholinguistics (theory of speech activity, speech production, speech perception, speech activity, speech mechanisms, etc.).

Let us consider the interaction of linguodidactics with a number of scientific disciplines related to language teaching. Among them are linguistics, psychology, sociology, communication theory, ethnology of communication, and didactics.

What is the place of linguistics among the scientific disciplines that feed the methodology of teaching a language - foreign and native? In all previous times, linguistics occupied the main place. Linguistic data (lexical units, morphology, rules of syntactic construction) were given a leading role in the process of teaching a language. This is so in the grammar-translation method (since the 40s of the XIX century), where the unit of study is the word and classes of words (grammar). The same

in direct methods (early XX century), only the unit is a more complex unit - a phrase. In audio-lingual and audio-visual methods (since the 50s of the XX century) - the structure of the sentence.

It should be noted that the methodology follows in its history the development of linguistic science: from neogrammarism to structuralism and transformational grammar and further to functionalism.

But in its current state, linguistics is characterized by a great diversity of subjects and units of study. Its main subjects, in addition to language, are speech, speech activity, speech subject, speech behavior, real processes of forming a speech message and its assimilation, the conditions in which they occur, and much more. And the methodology from private didactics becomes linguodidactics, since this diversity of subjects of linguistic consideration is also included in the methodology.

But linguodidactics is especially interested in how the speech subject (*homo loquens* - a speaking person) exists, i.e. in what psycholinguistics deals with. The issues of human linguistic existence will be considered in detail in the section "Psycholinguistic Foundations of Language Teaching", devoted to the speech subject, the environment of his speech existence, the unit of speech, communication and learning - the text - and the discipline that linguodidactics is concerned with teaching - language or speech activity.

The influence of psychology on the state of linguodidactic theory is very strong. The psychology of speech studies oral and written speech, external and internal speech, various aspects of speech activity, the speech subject; educational psychology addresses how knowledge, skills, and abilities are formed, how higher mental functions are implemented in the learning process; in the field of studying general psychology, the motivational sphere of activity of the speech subject (I.A. Zimnyaya), the problem of "speech and thinking" (L.S. Vygotsky, A.R. Luria, A.N. Leontiev); social psychology studies the speech behavior of different social groups, the language standard, or norm, socio-cultural aspects of communicative competence, understanding

as a socio-cultural process; and, of course, cognitive psychology, dealing with the psychology of cognitive processes, attracts close attention from linguodidactics.

In general, modern linguodidactics appears as a deeply psychologically rooted area of scientific knowledge. This will be discussed in the section "Psychological Foundations of Language Teaching", where the problems and state of scientific thought are considered in relation to man as an individual, as a subject of activity and as a subject of social life.

At the junction of linguistics and disciplines of the cultural direction in the 60s, two areas of knowledge emerged that very actively "cooperate" with linguodidactics. These are linguacultural studies and linguacultural studies.

Linguacultural studies studies the relationship and interaction of culture and language in its functioning, which creates the uniqueness of the national linguistic picture of the world. Of particular interest is the study of language as a system in which the values of culture are embodied. Linguacultural studies developed in the depths of the methodology of teaching language as an area of knowledge about the realities of the country of the studied language and the ways of expressing them in language, lexical and phraseological.

Its problematic is the identification of linguistic means of national and cultural use and methods of teaching students linguistic and cultural material).

The methodology appears as a social discipline.

Education is one of the social processes, it ensures the reproduction of social experience, its transfer from one generation to another, from one social group to other communities of individuals. In sociology, such a process as translation is studied.

This is a material transfer of elements from one state to another, the restoration of the state according to standards or samples. Education arose in the history of society as a means of overcoming the gap that arose in the process of reproduction, when simple forms of activity translation became impossible, namely: the transition from one production activity to another of the people themselves, the bearers of the activity or the transfer of products (G.P. Shchedrovitsky). Social problems discussed in

linguodidactics: social order of society, needs, demand and expectations of society from language teaching, a system of views on teaching, including a system of scientific views.

At the very beginning of the presentation, the initial connection between methodology and didactics was noted. Didactics (learning theory) is a scientific discipline that emerged much earlier than methodology. It has accumulated a significant amount of ideas about the laws of the learning and acquisition process, including reliance on experience, accumulation of acquisition material, and analytical activity. Didactics has identified a chain of cognitive activity of the learning subject: from perception to imprinting (unconscious memorization), from imprinting to activation of existing ideas and their imposition on the perceived experience, then an addition to the previous experience occurs and the actual development of new experience as new formations of the personality in the form of judgments, skills, and experiences.

It can be argued that methodology as a science is an exclusively applied field of knowledge, the focus of which is the practice of teaching.

Definition Methodology of language teaching, or linguodidactics, studies the existing practice of teaching, the problem of how to teach a language: goals, programs, content of training, subjects of training, their needs, etc., technologies and methods of teaching, generalizing them in the form of integral systems that are implemented in specific courses of study.

Methodology of language teaching also appears as a science that accumulates ideas about teaching methods.

Below is a brief excursion into the history of the science of language teaching. It is a relatively young field of knowledge. The beginning of reflection on how the process of language teaching occurs dates back to the first half of the 19th century for Western Europe.

Conscious-practical method: Shcherba L.V., L.S. Vygotsky, B.V. Belyaev, A.A. Mirolyubov, S.F. Shatilov, M.V. Lyakhovitsky, N.I. Gez, A.A. Leontiev, R.K. Minyar-Beloruhev.

Direct methods: Berlitz, Palmer.

Audio-lingual method: Parker. Sentence as the basic unit of learning. Distributive analysis, L. Bloomfield's theory of language, transformational grammar. Models of speech behavior based on the theory of behaviorism (USA).

Audio-visual method: objectively selected vocabulary, b) more natural-sounding dialogues, c) active forms of learning, d) priority to spoken language in the form of dialogues; d) absence or little presence of explanations of the rules given in the form of illustrations, examples, model phrases; e) teaching written speech with a significant delay (after 100 hours of classes); g) sound or visual supports (questions, comics, exercises to choose from, etc.).

Functional methods: R. Jakobson, Sh. Bally, F. Bruno.

6 functions: phatic, emotive, referential, poetic, etc. Speech act theory: Austin and Searle.

Communicative method: E.I.Passov, H.-E.Pifo, P.Corder.

Intensive methods: G.A.Kitaigorodskaya, I.Yu.Shekhter, V.V.Petrusinsky.

From the history of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language: S.G.Barkhudarov (1967), V.G.Kostomarov, O.D.Mitrofanova (1976 - Methodological guide for teaching Russian as a foreign language to foreigners; 1990 - Methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language); A.A.Akishina, O.E.Kagan (1997 - Learning to teach. What you need to know about teaching Russian as a foreign language); L.V.Moskovkin (1997).

At the end of this article we will present the diagram "Fundamental bases of linguodidactics" in which the main attention is paid to the scientific bases of language teaching: psychological, psycholinguistic and didactic. In the center is the figure of the learner as a subject of life, activity, educational activity, speech (see Fig. 1).

1st scheme.

The anthropological paradigm in education has the humanitarian as its dominant feature. Humanitarianism is understood as the property of giving priority to the human dimension in social processes, as the quality of relations in activity and attitude to activity, manifested in the recognition of the value of an individual. The very content of life changes towards humanization. We can talk about the humanitarian orientation of the environment, reflected in education. The education system prioritizes the tasks of human development, where we are not talking about the harmonious development of the individual, corresponding to a certain "moral code", but about the development of a person as his self-development, about the orientation towards the development of individuals and the widespread provision of this development by removing the main age, social and organizational restrictions. Humanitarian content is focused on the value system of individual thinking, creativity and subjective organization of the learning process, on the ability of a student to independently choose the volume and level of assimilation of the educational program and responsibility for his choice. In order to form the personality of the student, to achieve a high level of his development, it is this activity that turns out to be more significant than the specific knowledge on a specific discipline that served as its basis.

The main characteristics of such a system of education are the autonomy (independence) of the student, the integrity of his involvement in the learning process and interaction with other participants in (life) activity.

At the same time, the student is called upon to share responsibility for his education with society. The semantic guidelines of modern education focus on a person, his role in the life of society, the formation of his own destiny, its construction, writing the text of his life. In this new situation, the content of education will be - we would say, without fear of truism - life. Life as an "internal act", as "self-realization, or - coming to oneself" - said (M. Mamardashvili).

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